

Factsheet #1

Persisting and emerging ethical issues in robot-assisted surgery

ROBOTS IN THE OPERATING THEATRE

Although the exact definition may vary, robot-assisted surgery (RAS) can broadly be specified as a surgical technology where a programmable robot capable of processing complex data is placed between a human surgeon and a patient and has the ability to place or assist in the placing of surgical instruments in the patient.

The first technological steps towards RAS can be traced back to the 1970s. Since the 1990s, RAS devices have become commercially available. It wasn't until the last decade, however, that RAS gained traction.^{1,2} Since then, there has been a steady increase in use of RAS, especially in the US, UK, Germany, and Japan. This increase even led to RAS becoming the standard of care (i.e., the recommended procedure) in some fields. Currently, there are around 40 different robotic systems commercially available.^{3,4,5}

The most ubiquitously used and well-known among them is the Da Vinci surgical system from

The rise of the robots

Increase of estimated caseload in general surgery from 2012 to 2018 in US hospitals

Intuitive Surgical, a US-based biotechnology company. There are around 10.000 Da Vinci surgical systems currently in use worldwide, and they have, by some estimations, performed around 14 million surgical procedures, thus far.^{6,7}

Ethical issues in robot-assisted surgery

While ethical issues surrounding the use of RAS have been noted early on in the technological development, compared to other medical technologies operating in close proximity to patients in vulnerable states, RAS has received comparably little attention from the medical ethics community. With reference to the currently available literature, we determine at least six persisting and

tightly interconnected ethical domains of discussion that mark the primary orientation points in the landscape of ethical issues in RAS.

Benefits and harms

It has been agreed upon, in keeping with well-known ethical principles of avoidance of harm and beneficence, that patients' benefit is one of the primary criteria in determining the appropriate use of RAS. On many occasions, however, empirical evidence with regard to such benefits remains scarce, is very domain-specific and often inferior in quality, warranting a very careful evaluation of potential harms and benefits. Risks to data security and patient privacy need to be included in ethical considerations. It should be noted, however, that RAS may present the opportunity for significant advantages to the surgical profession, ameliorating the strain of bodily and mentally demanding

Harms and benefits are key criteria of ethical evaluation. Whether these can be met is very device-specific

work in the operating theater.

Responsibility and control

The ability to assign responsibility to a human agent in the interplay of surgeons, robots, and manufacturers is critical to avoid questions of diffusion of or gaps in responsibility. This applies in a prospective sense with regard to obligations and duties to ensure ethically favourable conditions of use of RAS, as well as in a retrospective sense with

The ability to assign responsibility to a human agent is critical to avoid so-called responsibility gaps.

a view to malfunctions, damage, and medical errors.

Surgical training and learning

RAS requires to acquire specific skill sets to ensure competence, raising the question as to how surgical learning and especially patient involvement ought to be organized. Surgical learning programs for RAS often show considerable shortcomings in credentialing and certification raising questions of patient safety. These weaknesses, alongside the manual nature of surgical learning, place special and strict responsibilities on surgeons to seek nec-

essary competence, be aware of its limitations and account for them in clinical decision making.

Introducing RAS as surgical innovation

Surgical innovation in RAS and surgical treatment are tightly connected. Surgeons hold a double role as researchers and innovators as well as medical experts in patient care. This creates difficult tensions between their duties and obligations which need to be discussed as part of the development of RAS. While on the one hand surgeons should neither unnecessarily delay nor rush potentially beneficial but risky innovations into patient care, their role as key stakeholders in the innovation process requires continuous efforts towards undiscovered grounds. Ethical grey zones in surgical innovation are known and common but need to be avoided.

Financial incentives and economic pressure

It has been noted that the intersection of healthcare and economy in RAS puts external pressure on healthcare decisions connected to RAS, which need to be navigated from an ethical perspective.

This applies to the dual role of surgeons as well as to institutional arrangements of RAS and economic interests of manufacturers.

Relational aspects

Surgeons and medical teams must adapt to newly introduced technologies, potentially changing social practices in the field or creating new effects of codependency with ethical implications. This may include an ethically concerning diminishing of human skills in competence as well as in control, which are vital in unforeseeable situations. The increased distance between surgeons and patients (especially in telesurgery) and the mediating nature of RAS have also raised concerns of trust and relational integrity.

Future directions

With a view to this landscape, we assess that questions of responsibility for and control over RAS, relational aspects and human-machine- interaction and questions of competence, learning, and skills heavily depend on the capacities of available robots and will very likely be influenced by foreseeable future developments in RAS towards more autonomous devices.

Several authors have put forward classification systems, aiming to categorize the current and foreseeable developments of RAS. These classi-

represent their surroundings and to react to them variably, we deem it likely that coming generations of RAS will exceed the current capacities by far.

More autonomous and more complex machines in RAS will have a decisive impact on questions of responsibility and control. This applies to the extent to which humans can and should be in control of RAS procedures as well as to ethical questions regarding prospective and especially retrospective responsibilities. In addition, those questions will emerge in close proximity to ethical issues of human-machine interactions in a more general sense. This will require a reassessment of the distribution of tasks between team members, surgeons, and robots as well as answers to difficult

Increasing levels of functional robot autonomy

fication systems highlight increasing functional autonomy as the major developmental path, in line with the assessment that current devices may present a bridge technology between traditional approaches to laparoscopic surgery and autonomous surgical robots.

In close proximity to classification systems in self-driving cars, these considerations place currently available robotic systems in surgery at low levels of autonomy. Projects in research and development, however, increasingly exceed these levels and, e.g., allow for autonomous execution of pre-approved operation plans under human oversight. Given the recent developments in artificial intelligence and the increasing abilities of machines to

ethical questions with regard to professional surgeons' autonomy and their ability to prioritize the patients' benefit and well-being at all times.

Finally, it seems very likely that there will be a gradual and ongoing shift in questions of learning and competencies, requiring technical knowledge, competences, and literacy in data and digitization as part of the virtues to be maintained by the robotic surgeons besides their classic skill set to be able to deal with these challenges.

Future ethical research

Given the shift of RAS towards an increased functional autonomy, we note the need for a readjust-

ment of ethical research perspectives. While the ethical discourse usually addresses robotic devices in surgery from an instrumental perspective, highlighting their role as means to agents' ends, the increase of functional autonomy requires to broaden this perspective to be able to encompass and allow an analysis of ethical questions emerging with more autonomous devices.

References

- ¹ Attanasio, Aleks; Scaglioni, Bruno; Momi, Elena de; Fiorini, Paolo; Valdastrì, Pietro (2021): Autonomy in Surgical Robotics. In: Annu. Rev. Control Robot. Auton. Syst. 4 (1), S. 651–679. DOI: 10.1146/annurev-control-062420-090543.
- ² Pugin, F.; Bucher, P.; Morel, P. (2011): History of robotic surgery: from AESOP® and ZEUS® to da Vinci®. In: Journal of visceral surgery 148 (5 Suppl), e3-8. DOI: 10.1016/j.jviscsurg.2011.04.007.
- ³ Sheetz, Kyle H.; Claflin, Jake; Dimick, Justin B. (2020): Trends in the Adoption of Robotic Surgery for Common Surgical Procedures. In: JAMA Network Open 3 (1), e1918911. DOI: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2019.18911.
- ⁴ Chung, Gary; Hinoul, Piet; Coplan, Paul; Yoo, Andrew (2021): Trends in the Diffusion of Robotic Surgery in Prostate, Uterus, and Colorectal Procedures: A Retrospective Population-Based Study. In: Journal of Robotic Surgery 15 (2), S. 275–291. DOI: 10.1007/s11701-020-01102-6.
- ⁵ Cepolina, Francesco; Razzoli, Roberto P. (2022): An Introductory Review of Robotically Assisted Surgical Systems. In: The International Journal of Medical Robotics and Computer Assisted Surgery 18 (4), e2409. DOI: 10.1002/rcs.2409.
- ⁶ Da Vinci Robotic Surgical Systems | Intuitive (2025). Online available <https://www.intuitive.com/en-us/products-and-services/da-vinci>.
- ⁷ Intuitive Surgical, Inc. (2025): Annual Report on Form 10-K for the fiscal year ended December 31, 2024. Form 10-K. Intuitive Surgical, Inc (0001035267-25-000017). Online available <https://isrg.intuitive.com/static-files/3606b65a-c676-47a5-a638-6b53c19b7143>.

Recommendations for further reading

- Ficuciello, Fanny; Hossein Hamedani, Mohammad; Tamburrini, Guglielmo (2024): Meaningful human control of increasingly autonomous robots for surgery. In Giulio Mecacci, Daniele Amoroso, Luciano Cavalcante Siebert, David Abbink, Jeroen den van Hoven, Filippo Santoni (Eds.): Research handbook on meaningful human control of artificial intelligence systems. Cheltenham, UK, Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 205–231.
- Hutchison, Katrina; Johnson, Jane; Carter, Drew (2016): Justice and Surgical Innovation: The Case of Robotic Prostatectomy. In Bioethics 30 (7), pp. 536–546. DOI: 10.1111/bioe.12252.
- Power, David (2024): Ethical considerations in the era of AI, automation, and surgical robots: there are

plenty of lessons from the past. In Discov Artif Intell 4 (1), pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1007/s44163-024-00166-9.

Wah, Jack Ng Kok (2025): The rise of robotics and AI-assisted surgery in modern healthcare. In Journal of robotic surgery 19 (1), p. 311. DOI: 10.1007/s11701-025-02485-0.

Read the full report

Haltaufderheide, Joschka; Pfisterer-Heise, Stefanie; Pieper, Dawid; Ranisch, Robert (2024): The ethical landscape of robot-assisted surgery. A systematic review. Online available <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2411.11637>.

About the Digital Medical Ethics Network

Digitalization is rapidly changing the healthcare system and is having an increasing impact on practice. The use of new artificial intelligence technologies in diagnosis and therapy, mobile health applications on smartphones or the use of robotics holds a wide range of potential. However, it is also associated with ethical risks. Understanding these challenges and dealing with them is the task of medical ethics. Researchers need new knowledge and skills for this. The aim of the new Digital Medical Ethics Network (DiMEN) is to support them in this task by conducting research, developing freely available resources and strengthening networks among researchers. <https://www.digitalemedicalethics.net>

About the authors

Dr. Joschka Haltaufderheide

is research associate at the Juniorprofessorship for Medical Ethics with a Focus of Digitization. He is working in the field of ethics of new bio- and health technologies and philosophy of technology.

Prof. Dr. Robert Ranisch

is Juniorprofessor for Medical Ethics with a Focus of Digitization. His research interests include fundamental questions of Medical Ethics, especially related to digitization and technologies.

Contact us

For more Information about our activities please contact

Prof. Dr. Robert Ranisch
Juniorprofessorship for Medical Ethics
with a Focus on Digitization
Faculty of Health Sciences Brandenburg
University of Potsdam
ranisch@uni-potsdam.de

Cite this factsheet

Haltaufderheide, J., & Ranisch, R. (2024). Persisting and emerging ethical issues in robot-assisted surgery. Digital Medical Ethics Network. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17222580>